

Kenneth L Londoner [founded the medical device company BioSig Technologies](#) in February 2009. This company has created a system designed to improve Atrial Fibrillation and Ventricular Tachycardia, called PURE EP. This is a surface electrocardiogram (ECG) and intracardiac multichannel recording and analysis system. Kenneth L Londoner serves as the CEO of BioSig.

Besides of this, Londoner serves as the Managing Partner of Endicott Management Partners, LLC. This is a company that assists emerging growth companies in their corporate development and investing needs.

Over the course of his career, Kenneth L Londoner has held a number of positions in different companies, and also founded and co-founded other companies, besides BioSig.

From April 2007 to October 2009, Kenneth L Londoner has held a position as the executive vice president of the Silicon Valley based cardiac software company, NewCardio, Inc.

From May 2012 to March 2014, he held a position as the Director and the architect for the turnaround at Alliqua BioMedical, Inc.

Kenneth L Londoner co-founded a port security and logistics company, Safe Ports Holdings. This company is based in Charleston, South Carolina.

Moreover, in 1996, Kenneth L Londoner founded Red Coat Capital Management. He serves as its managing partner. This hedge fund has grown from its initial base of \$ 2 million in assets to a peak of \$ 1.1 billion.

Currently, he is working on commercialization of the PURE EP System, which was [approved by FDA](#).